

Bridging the Gap between Academia and Industry: Transforming the Universal Variability Language to pure::variants and back – Online Appendix

Dario Romano
LIT CPS Lab
Johannes Kepler University Linz
Linz, Austria
dario.romano@jku.at

Kevin Feichtinger
LIT CPS Lab
Johannes Kepler University Linz
Linz, Austria
kevin.feichtinger@jku.at

Danilo Beuche
pure-systems GmbH
Madgeburg, Germany
danilo.beuche@pure-systems.com

Uwe Ryssel
pure-systems GmbH
Madgeburg, Germany
uwe.ryssel@pure-systems.com

Rick Rabiser
CDL VaSiCS, LIT CPS Lab
Johannes Kepler University Linz
Linz, Austria
rick.rabiser@jku.at

1 INTRODUCTION

Variability models are used in Software Product Lines (SPLs) to explicitly capture the commonalities and variabilities of a set of software(-intensive) systems [3]. Many variability modeling approaches have been developed in the last 30 years [1, 3, 6, 8, 13, 14]. Feature modeling and decision modeling are the most common approaches with many variants [7]. Other, often domain-specific approaches developed by academia and industry exist [2, 4, 9, 11, 15]. Despite multiple attempts, no standard variability modeling approach [10, 16] is currently available.

This document is the online appendix of the paper *Bridging the Gap between Academia and Industry: Transforming the Universal Variability Language to pure::variants and back*¹. The paper presents how we implemented transformations between the commercial pure::variants [12] and the Universal Variability Language (UVL) [16]. The pure::variants approach was originally presented in 2008 and since then developed and extended to become a commercially successful variability modeling tool [5]. UVL is developed by the MODEVAR community (<https://modevar.github.io/>) and represents a first step towards a unified variability modeling approach. In the appendix, we present and describe the algorithms implemented based on the mapping table in the paper.

With our work, we bridge the gap between academic and industrial variability modeling approaches and bring their tools closer together, e.g., allow academic models to be imported into pure::variants and industrial variability models into academic tools to experiment with the capabilities the different tools provide.

2 ALGORITHMS

Recognizing relations from propositional logic constraints is handled by a number of algorithms in our approach. In the paper we described the ideas behind these algorithms in section 4. After parsing the UVL model from a file, the highest level Algorithm 1 shows the most basic steps of the transformation process. First the features of the pure::variants feature tree are built and constraints are collected. Afterwards the constraints are translated and, if desired

by the user, optimized. In the last step the relations are assigned to their owner features and the translation concludes.

Algorithm 1 Convert model from UVL to pure::variants

```
1: function ADDDATATOMODEL(uolModel, optimize)
2:   uolRoot ← uolModel.getRootFeatures()[0]
3:   uolConstraints ← uolModel.getConstraints()
4:   pvModel ← createModel(uolRoot.getName())
5:   pvRoot ← pvModel.getRoot()
6:   buildFeaturesRecursively( $\emptyset$ , pvRoot, uolRoot, MANDATORY)
7:   translateConstraints(constraints)           ▷ constraints is a global
8:   if optimize then
9:     optimize(relations)                       ▷ relations is a global
10:  end if
11:  assignConstraints(relations)
12:  return pvModel
13: end function
```

Algorithm 2 recursively takes a given UVL feature and transfers its attributes to a pure::variants feature. It then checks all UVL-groups owned by the current UVL feature, and calls itself for each child. It then sets the cardinality accordingly for every child feature.

Algorithm 2 Recursively create pure::variants tree

```
1: function BUILDFEATURESRECURSIVELY(pvParent, pvCur, uolCur, card)
2:   pvCur ← uolCur.getName()
3:   if pvParent ≠  $\emptyset$  then
4:     pvCur.createID()
5:   end if
6:   addFeatureToModel(pvCur, pvParent, card)
7:   addAttributes(pvCur, uolCur)
8:   for group ∈ uolCur do
9:     newCard ← group.getCardinality()
10:    range ← group.getRange()
11:    for feat ∈ group.getChildren() do
12:      child ← new pvFeature()
13:      buildFeaturesRecursively(pvCur, child, feat, newCard)
14:    end for
15:    if range ≠  $\emptyset$  then
16:      for child ∈ pvCur.getOrGroup() do
17:        child.setRange(range)
18:      end for
19:    end if
20:  end for
21: end function
```

¹<https://doi.org/xx.yyyy/zzzzzz.zzzzzz>

After building the feature tree for pure::variants the list of constraints at the end of the UVL file is translated. Algorithm 3 receives the entire list of constraints and tries to find an appropriate translation method from very basic structural information.

Algorithm 3 UVL constraint to relation or pvSCL constraint

```

1: function TRANSLATECONSTRAINTS(constraints)
2:   for constraint  $\in$  constraints do
3:     if constraint.isImpliesOrEquals() then
4:       if constraint.left().size() > 1 then
5:         complexLeft(constraint)
6:       else
7:         simpleLeft(constraint)
8:       end if
9:     else if constraint.isOrAndNot() then
10:      if (count(Equals,constraint)+count(Implies,constraint))>1 then
11:        handleMultiPartConstraint(constraint)
12:      else
13:        if !reconstructRelation(constraint.cnf()) then
14:          translateToPvSCL(constraint)
15:        end if
16:      end if
17:    else
18:      throw TranslationsException()
19:    end if
20:  end for
21: end function

```

If the constraint has an implication or equivalence as top-level logic operator, it first checks if it immediately can identify a potential owner on the left side, by checking if there is exactly one literal. Depending on the amount of literals, either Algorithm 6 or Algorithm 7 continue the analysis. If the top-level logic operator is either \vee or \wedge it is check if multiple implications or equivalences exist within the constraint. Algorithm 4 handles cases like this. If the top level operator is \vee the entire constraint is attempted to be de- and reconstructed by Algorithm 5, and if it is \wedge the individual terms connected by it get the same treatment, to receive more, but simpler constraints.

Algorithm 4 Handles constraints with multiple implications or equivalences.

```

1: function HANDLEMULTIPARTCONSTRAINT(c)
2:   cnfForm  $\leftarrow$  c.cnf()
3:   if c.topLevelOperator =  $\vee$  then
4:     if !reconstructRelation(c) then
5:       createPvSCL(c)
6:     end if
7:   else if c.topLevelOperator =  $\wedge$  then
8:     for term  $\in$  cnfForm do
9:       if !reconstructRelation(c) then
10:        createPvSCL(c)
11:       end if
12:     end for
13:   end if
14: end function

```

Algorithm 5 generally performs the transformation to CNF and reconstruction into one of three relation-types described in section 4. As a fallback, Algorithms 4, 3,5 all translate the originally passed constraint into pvSCL, should the reconstruction fail.

Continuing the case that the crude analysis of a constraint could identify a potential owner on the left side of a constraint, Algorithm 6 analysis the structure on the right side, to either hand the final recognition step to Algorithm 8 or Algorithm 11. If a sign

Algorithm 5 Deconstructs a logic formula and tries to reconstruct it into a relation.

```

1: function RECONSTRUCTRELATION(c)
2:   posLiterals  $\leftarrow$  c.getPositiveLiterals()
3:   negLiterals  $\leftarrow$  c.getNegativeLiterals()
4:   if posLiterals =  $\emptyset$   $\wedge$  negLiterals > 0 then
5:     create(negLiterals[0] conflicts(negLiterals[1 ... size]))
6:     return true
7:   else if posLiterals > 0  $\wedge$  negLiterals = 1 then
8:     create(negLiterals[0] requires(posLiterals))
9:     return true
10:  else if posLiterals = 1  $\wedge$  negLiterals > 0 then
11:    create(posLiterals[0] requiredForAll(negLiterals))
12:    return true
13:  else if posLiterals > 0  $\wedge$  negLiterals = 0 then
14:    create(root requires(posLiterals))
15:    return true
16:  end if return false
17: end function

```

that the right part of the constraints can not be translated into a relation-type, the pvSCL fallback is used here as well.

Algorithm 6 Analyze the structure of a constraint with a simple left part.

```

1: function SIMPLELEFT(c)
2:   if hasNegatedLiteral(c.left()) then
3:     createPvSCL(c,c.right())
4:   else
5:     if c.right.literals().size()>1 then
6:       simpleLeftComplexRight(c)
7:     else
8:       simpleLeftSimpleRight(c)
9:     end if
10:  end if
11: end function

```

Should the left side of the constraint already have more than one literal Algorithm 7 will try to create a DNF, split the terms connected by the top-level \vee and translate each of the terms as their own constraint with the given original right part of the complex constraint. If it's not possible to create an acceptable DNF, the Algorithm either resorts to a more in-depth analysis through Algorithm 11 or another Algorithm that functions similar to Algorithm 10.

Should the structure of a constraint be an implication or equivalence, with only one literal on each side, Algorithm 8 can in most cases easily recognize a fitting relation type. Only in case the top-level operator is an *equals*, and the right side is negated, we have to resort to pvSCL, because there is no relation-type that can model this constraint.

Similar to other of the described algorithms, Algorithm 10 attempts to recognize a structure that can be directly translated into a relation. Since it only receives constraint with more than one literal on the right side of an equivalence or implication, it attempts to create a CNF of the right side of the constraint, and potentially split by a \wedge operator. This split constraints receive the same left a side and operator as the original constraint, but limit the right side to one term of the CNF per constraint. As a fallback we also use pvSCL here.

Algorithm 11 has already been shown in the original paper. It handles the most complex case of a constraint with a single equivalence or implication as top-level operator. Since it cannot directly

Algorithm 7 Further analyze the structure of a constraint with a complex left part.

```

1: function COMPLEXLEFT(c)
2:   if anythingNegated(c.left()) then
3:     dnfLeft ← toDNF(c.left())
4:     if dnfLeft.topLevelOperator() = ∨ then
5:       for term ∈ dnfLeft do
6:         if c.topLevelOperator() = ⇒ then
7:           translateConstraints(term ⇒ c.right())
8:         else
9:           translateConstraints(term ⇔ c.right())
10:        end if
11:      end for
12:    else
13:      if c.right().size() > 1 then
14:        createPvSCL(c, ∅)
15:      else
16:        createPvSCL(c, c.right())
17:      end if
18:    end if
19:  else
20:    if c.right().literals().size() > 1 then
21:      complexLeftComplexRight(c)
22:    else
23:      complexLeftSimpleRight(c)
24:    end if
25:  end if
26: end function

```

Algorithm 8 Recognizes a constraint with simple structures on the right and left side of the top level operator and converts it to relations.

```

1: function SIMPLELEFTSIMPLERIGHT(c)
2:   if hasNegativeLiteral(c.right()) then
3:     if c.topLevelOperator() = ⇒ then
4:       create(c.right() conflicts(c.left().literals()))
5:     else if c.topLevelOperator() = ⇔ then
6:       createPvSCL(c)
7:     end if
8:   else
9:     if c.topLevelOperator() = ⇒ then
10:      create(c.left() requires(c.right().literals()))
11:    else if c.topLevelOperator() = ⇔ then
12:      create(c.left() equalsAll(c.right().literals()))
13:    end if
14:  end if
15: end function

```

identify an owner from the given structure, it will always try to either split the left or the right side of the top-level operator to create a number of simpler constraint, which can then be recursively analyzed starting with Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 9 shows the process of merging multiple similar relations into a single, logically equivalent, relation. As hinted at in the main paper, it checks within a single owner if multiple relations of the same type *requiresAll*, *requiredFor*, *equalsAll* or *conflictsAny* exist, and then merges their targets into a single relation of the same type. We call these relation types merge-able relations in the paper. If it finds relations of type *requires*, *requiredForAll*, *equalsAny* or *conflicts* that have exactly one target, it tries to find a corresponding merge-able relation to merge its target into. If none does exist, and multiple relations of the same non-merge-able relation-type, with the corner case of one target, exist, it tries to merge them into a new merge-able relation.

Algorithm 9 Optimise relations for a list of owners.

```

1: function OPTIMIZE(owners)
2:   for owner ∈ owners do
3:     for relType ∈ relTypes do
4:       if relType.isMergeableType() then
5:         targets ← owner.getRelsOf(relType).getTargets()
6:         owner.getRelsOf(relType).removeAll()
7:         owner.addRelation(new Relation(owner, relType, targets))
8:       else
9:         targets ← owner.getRelsOf(relType.filter(targets.size=1).getTargets())
10:        owner.getRelsOf(relType.filter(targets.size=1).removeAll())
11:        if owner.hasRelationToMergeInto(relType) then
12:          owner.getRelToMergeInto(relType).add(targets)
13:        else
14:          owner.addRelation(new
15:            Relation(owner, mergeableType(relType), targets))
16:        end if
17:      end for
18:    end for
19: end function

```

Algorithm 10 Translates a constraint with simple left and complex right.

```

1: function SIMPLELEFTCOMPLEXRIGHT(c)
2:   cnfRight ← c.cnf()
3:   if cnfRight.contains(∨) then
4:     if cnfRight.contains(∧) then
5:       for term ∈ cnfRight do
6:         if c.topLevelOperator() = ⇒ then
7:           translateConstraints(c.left() ⇒ term)
8:         else
9:           translateConstraints(c.left() ⇔ term)
10:        end if
11:      end for
12:    else
13:      if anythingNegated(cnfRight) then
14:        createPvSCL(c)
15:      else
16:        if c.topLevelOperator() = ⇒ then
17:          create(c.left() requires(c.right().literals()))
18:        else
19:          create(c.left() equalsAny(c.right().literals()))
20:        end if
21:      end if
22:    end if
23:  else
24:    if anythingNegated(cnfRight) then
25:      for term ∈ cnfRight do
26:        if c.topLevelOperator() = ⇒ then
27:          translateConstraints(c.left() ⇒ term)
28:        else
29:          translateConstraints(c.left() ⇔ term)
30:        end if
31:      end for
32:    else
33:      if c.topLevelOperator() = ⇒ then
34:        create(c.left() requiresAll(c.right().literals()))
35:      else
36:        create(c.left() equalsAll(c.right().literals()))
37:      end if
38:    end if
39:  end if
40: end function

```

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Algorithm 11 Translate a constraint that has more than one literal on both sides of a *implies/equivalence* top-level operator.

```

1: function COMPLEXLEFTCOMPLEXRIGHT(c)
2:   if !c.left().contains(∧) then
3:     cnfRight ← c.right().cnf()
4:     if cnfRight.contains(∧) then
5:       for term ∈ cnfRight do
6:         if c.topLevelOperator = ⇒ then
7:           translateConstraints(c.left() ⇒ term)
8:         else
9:           translateConstraints(c.left() ⇔ term)
10:        end if
11:      end for
12:    else
13:      if optimize then
14:        !reconstructRelation(c.cnf) then
15:          createPvSCL(c)
16:        end if
17:      else
18:        createPvSCL(c)
19:      end if
20:    end if
21:  else
22:    if !c.left().contains(∧) then
23:      for literal ∈ c.left().literals() do
24:        if c.topLevelOperator = ⇒ then
25:          translateConstraints(literal ⇒ c.right())
26:        else
27:          translateConstraints(literal ⇔ c.right())
28:        end if
29:      end for
30:    else
31:      cnfRight ← c.right().cnf()
32:      if cnfRight.topLevelOperator=∧ then
33:        for term ∈ cnfRight do
34:          if c.topLevelOperator = ⇒ then
35:            translateConstraints((c.left() ⇒ term))
36:          else
37:            translateConstraints(c.left() ⇔ term)
38:          end if
39:        end for
40:      end if
41:    end if
42:  end if
43: end function

```

REFERENCES

- [1] Rabih Bashroush, Muhammad Garba, Rick Rabiser, Iris Groher, and Goetz Botterweck. 2017. Case tool support for variability management in software product lines. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* 50, 1 (2017), 14:1–14:45.
- [2] Maurice H. ter Beek, Klaus Schmid, and Holger Eichelberger. 2019. Textual Variability Modeling Languages: An Overview and Considerations. In *Proceedings of the 23rd International Systems and Software Product Line Conference - Volume B (SPLC '19)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 151–157.
- [3] Thorsten Berger, Ralf Rublack, Divya Nair, Joanne M. Atlee, Martin Becker, Krzysztof Czarnecki, and Andrzej Wasowski. 2013. A survey of variability modeling in industrial practice. In *Proc. of the 7th International Workshop on Variability Modelling of Software-intensive Systems*. ACM, 7–14.
- [4] Thorsten Berger, Steven She, Rafael Lotufo, Andrzej Wasowski, and Krzysztof Czarnecki. 2010. Variability modeling in the real: a perspective from the operating systems domain. In *Proc. of the IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering*. ACM, 73–82.
- [5] D. Beuche. 2008. Modeling and Building Software Product Lines with Pure:Variants. In *Software Product Line Conference, International*. IEEE Computer Society, Los Alamitos, CA, USA, 358. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SPLC.2008.53>
- [6] Lianping Chen and Muhammad Ali Babar. 2011. A systematic review of evaluation of variability management approaches in software product lines. *Information and Software Technology* 53, 4 (2011), 344–362.
- [7] Krzysztof Czarnecki, Paul Grünbacher, Rick Rabiser, Klaus Schmid, and Andrzej Wasowski. 2012. Cool Features and Tough Decisions: A Comparison of Variability Modeling Approaches. In *Proc. of the 6th International Workshop on Variability Modelling of Software-Intensive Systems*. ACM, 173–182.
- [8] Matthias Galster, Danny Weyns, Dan Tofan, Bartosz Michalik, and Paris Avgeriou. 2013. Variability in software systems—a systematic literature review. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 40, 3 (2013), 282–306.
- [9] Hassan Gomaa. 2005. *Designing software product lines with UML*. IEEE.
- [10] Øystein Haugen, Andrzej Wasowski, and Krzysztof Czarnecki. 2013. CVL: common variability language. In *Proc. of the 17th International Software Product Line Conference*. ACM, 277–277.
- [11] Klaus Pohl, Günter Böckle, and Frank J van der Linden. 2005. *Software Product Line Engineering: Foundations, Principles and Techniques*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- [12] pure-systems GmbH. 2022. pure::variants User’s Guide. <https://www.pure-systems.com/fileadmin/downloads/pure-variants/doc/pv-user-manual.pdf> Version 5.0.10.685, last access 2022-05-30.
- [13] Mikko Raatikainen, Juha Tiitonen, and Tomi Männistö. 2019. Software product lines and variability modeling: A tertiary study. *Journal of Systems and Software* 149 (2019), 485–510.
- [14] Pierre-Yves Schobbens, Patrick Heymans, and Jean-Christophe Trigaux. 2006. Feature diagrams: A survey and a formal semantics. In *Proc. of the 14th IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference*. IEEE, 139–148.
- [15] Steven She, Rafael Lotufo, Thorsten Berger, Andrzej Wasowski, and Krzysztof Czarnecki. 2010. The Variability Model of The Linux Kernel. In *Proc. of the 5th International Workshop on Variability Modelling of Software-intensive Systems*. ACM, 45–51.
- [16] Chico Sundermann, Kevin Feichtinger, Dominik Engelhardt, Rick Rabiser, and Thomas Thüm. 2021. Yet Another Textual Variability Language? A Community Effort Towards a Unified Language. In *Proc. of the 25th International Systems and Software Product Line Conference*. ACM, Leicester, United Kingdom.